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Workplace learning experienced by employees in information technology-enabled work environments – a developing country experiences

Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of this paper is to present the findings of a study that investigated workplace learning activities and drivers that enhanced learning as experienced by employees in Sri Lanka.

Design/methodology/approach: The study was conducted in the knowledge process outsourcing sector, where employees perform knowledge work in flatter team-based structures with IT-enabled work environments. From the 17 firms that volunteered to participate in the study, 239 technical/professional employees volunteered for the survey. Multiple regression analysis was used to identify the association between drivers of workplace learning and learning activities experienced by employees, and whether individual demographic characteristics and the number of employees in the firm are associated with workplace learning activities experienced by employees.

Findings: The study found that organization-related, individual-related, and team-related drivers significantly influence workplace learning activities experienced by employees. In addition, employees' age, firm-specific experience, and the number of employees in the firm significantly influence the same.

Originality/value: The paper presents learning activities experienced by employees in the completion of work-related job tasks at hand and drivers experienced by employees in the new normal that exists since the Covid-19 pandemic.

Keywords: workplace learning; IT-enabled work environment; peer learning; teams; Sri Lanka

Paper type: Research paper

Workplace learning experienced by employees in information technology-enabled work environments – a developing country experiences

Introduction

Workplace learning is understood as a process where employees acquire knowledge, skills, and attitudes for the completion of job roles, which could foster desirable and sustainable outcomes for employees and organisations (Matthews, 1999; Moon and Na, 2009). First and foremost, workplace learning develops knowledge, skills, and attitudes needed by employees to perform job roles at hand. It is expected that workplace learning facilitates more effective decision-making and problem-solving at work. Second, learning for work leads an individual to learn about him/herself, which leads to identity construction and transformation (Billett, 2010; Filliettaz, 2013; Van Dellen and Cohen-Scali, 2015). This identity construction and transformation through workplace learning is crucial in the present-day flexible labour markets, where many organisations maintain laissez-faire attitude when supporting employees' career development. Third, the enhanced performance of employees due to workplace learning eventually leads to better equip organisations for competition in domestic and international markets in the long run.

The study was conducted in the offshore knowledge process outsourcing (KPO) sector in Sri Lanka, where services are provided to foreign clients using the power of information technology (IT). During the last two decades, a considerable number of KPO operations were established and helped to create types of jobs that have not existed in the country before. In these organizations, employees perform work in flatter team-based structures with IT-enabled work environments. The people-centric nature of services provided and the high rate of employee turnover in the KPO sector create challenges in the attraction and retention of personnel in terms of both quantity and quality (Wickramasinghe and Kumara, 2010). Hence, workplace learning activities are used immensely in bridging the knowledge and skill gaps of employees. In this context, the specific objectives of the present research were to investigate 1) workplace learning activities experienced by employees for the successful completion of work-related job tasks at hand, and 2) drivers that enhance workplace learning. In connection to the second objective, we tested two hypotheses, namely, drivers of workplace learning associated with learning activities experienced by employees (H1); and age, gender, marital status and the years of work experience of employees and the number of employees in the firm associated with workplace learning activities experienced by employees (H2). The relevant literature to support our objectives and hypotheses are reviewed in-depth in the section on *Literature Review*.

When considering the significance of the study, first, two types of management practices can be investigated, i.e., intended practices (identified as important but not implemented by the time of the study) or implemented practices (identified as important, and already implemented, and experienced by employees by the time of the study). Of these two, we investigated learning activities implemented and experienced by employees in the completion of work-related job tasks at hand. Identifying the most contributing learning activities are important to effectively bridge gaps in knowledge and skills as well as to get the maximum from limited resources that organizations could invest in employee learning. Second, in addition to learning activities experienced by employees, we investigated drivers that enhance learning. Conditions created after the Covid-19 pandemic demand the sharing of best practices (see Bierema, 2020; Hite and McDonald, 2020). Therefore, we believe that the findings derived from our study on drivers experienced by employees are valid in the new normal that exists since the Covid-19 pandemic. Third, interest in workplace learning stems from the quality and quantity of research in the developed West. However, Kim and McLean (2014) emphasised the importance of indigenization when foreign theories or practices of workplace learning are adopted by countries outside the developed West. We investigated workplace learning activities and drivers that could enhance learning as experienced by employees in a non-Western developing country, Sri Lanka. Hence, we believe the finding of our study provides new insight useful for practitioners, academics, researchers, and policymakers.

The rest of the paper is structured into five sections. The next section reviews the literature on workplace learning activities experienced by employees and drivers that could enhance learning. The methodology used in the study is then presented. Thereafter, results are presented and discussed along with the implications for theory and practice. Finally, conclusions are presented followed by the limitations of the study and areas for future research.

Literature review

Workplace learning activities

Workplace learning activities refer to opportunities available for employees to acquire knowledge and skills required to perform job tasks at the actual physical workplace location or at other locations (Govaerts and Baert, 2011; Moon and Na, 2009; Raemdonck et al., 2014). These cover a wide range of activities that are anchored in the organisation structure, culture, and work routines (refer to Govaerts and Baert, 2011 and Susomrith and Coetzer, 2015 for an extensive review of learning activities). In broad, these can be categorised into three main forms - formal, informal intentional, and informal unintentional (incidental) (Marsick and Watkins,

2001). Formal learning activities are institutionally sponsored deliberately created highly structured activities for learning. Some of the formal learning activities include courses, seminars, workshops, and conferences (Govaerts and Baert, 2011; Susomrith and Coetzer, 2015; Wang et al., 2010). In general, these formal activities are criticized for high cost, time consumption, and disconnection from day-to-day work (Van Rijn et al., 2013).

Typically, all learning activities outside formal are considered informal. An employee decides to learn if he/she feels the need for learning, and much of employees' learning in the workplace is identified to occur through informal activities (Susomrith and Coetzer, 2015; Van Rijn et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2010). Informal learning is categorised into either informal intentional or informal unintentional. According to Berg and Chyung (2008), informal intentional learning activities are integrated into job tasks, and therefore, are easier to observe, describe, and research than unintentional. Informal intentional learning activities include learning on the job through mentoring, coaching, supervision, asking questions, and receiving feedback (Berg and Chyung, 2008; Susomrith and Coetzer, 2015). Further, self-initiated learning, which denotes "an intentional, conscious pursuit on the part of the learner", is identified as informal intentional learning (Poell 2014, 19). When employees possess capabilities to self-initiate learning, they may seek out informal learning as their preferred method of learning. Furthermore, if employees work in teams, discussion forums and team meetings are identified as informal intentional learning, which assists in sharing knowledge, and eventually leads to gain new knowledge, skills, and abilities (Clarke, 2005; Van Rijn et al., 2013). Informal intentional learning in teams prospers when employees have avenues for team-based communication, knowledge sharing, and reflection. Overall, the success of informal intentional learning can largely be attributed to the capabilities of the individual and the quality of interactions he/she has with others.

Informal unintentional learning occurs from the unintended consequences, such as interpersonal interactions while executing daily tasks or learning from mistakes (Govaerts and Baert, 2011; Susomrith and Coetzer, 2015). An individual is often unaware of this type of learning due to not having both an intention to learn and an awareness of learning (Clarke, 2005). Since learning is not planned from the learner's point of view, the outcomes of informal unintentional learning are difficult to be predicted (Kyndt et al., 2009). Still, the learner could recognize and learn retrospectively if he/she possesses the required skills. Overall, organisations cannot solely rely on one method of learning, i.e., formal or informal (intentional or unintentional), and employees have to continuously engage in all types of learning activities for the effective performance of their job roles.

Drivers that enhance learning

In the present study, we define drivers that enhance learning to include systems created such as skill inventories or practices encouraged/facilitated such as team meetings by organisations as well as things that are not directly under the control of the organisation such as the enthusiasm of an employee to learn. In detail, the drivers created/facilitated by an organisation may include work systems, practices, policies, and the social environment that guide organizational decision-makers such as human resource managers and immediate supervisors, and employees on learning activities preferred by the organisation (Kyndt et al., 2009; Nikolova et al., 2016; Van der Sluis, 2004). In other words, conditions and occasions created by the organization and the existence of possibilities within the organization make certain workplace learning activities possible, preferred, and sustain. Evidence suggests that organisational policies, procedures, and support mechanisms for job enrichment, enlargement, and flexible work routines articulate how learning needs are to be fulfilled, and allow immediate supervisors to be creative in addressing the learning needs of subordinates (Kyndt et al., 2009; Nikolova et al., 2016). For example, employees' performance appraisal specifies performance expectations, the actual level of performance, learning needs, and how these needs could be addressed. The practices of providing structured learning experiences guided by immediate supervisors or in-house experts to newly hired employees can be identified as effective in making knowledge, skills, and attitudes preferred by the organisation more explicit. Such practices also align organisation's affordability with employee engagement in learning at work (Billett, 2015; Trede and McEwen, 2015). Further, the provision of avenues for reflection and sharing of successes/failures among team members enhance learning when employees work in teams and they are expected to collaborate in making decisions and problem-solving (Billett, 2015; Kyndt et al., 2009; Matsuo, 2016; Nikolova et al., 2016). Hence, support for social interactions, the removal of barriers for expression, and democratization could influence employees' learning from interpersonal interactions. Furthermore, challenging job content, provision of increased control over job tasks, and opportunities to experiment are identified to have a positive effect on individual learning (Reio and Wiswell, 2000). For example, reflections on work experience and challenging jobs tasks could influence an individual's level of engagement in workplace learning activities (Matsuo, 2016). An individual's drive for learning, achievement motivation, curiosity, and learning goal orientation is also identified to influence the choice of workplace learning activities (Kyndt et al., 2014; Moon and Na, 2009; Nitsche et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2010). Overall, based on the above-reviewed literature, we argue that drivers either under the control of

the organisation or employees are associated with the type of learning activities experienced by employees as stated as H1 in the section on *Introduction*.

Individual and firm characteristics as predictors of workplace learning

The literature suggests that individual characteristics affect workplace learning activities experienced by employees (Billett, 2015; Harteis et al., 2015). For example, Billett (2015) suggests that both the type of learning activities and the frequency of learning activities could be affected by the individual characteristics of employees. Further, Harteis et al. (2015), suggest that access to workplace learning activities is not evenly distributed among employees and even distribution is an important consideration in evaluating the quality of workplace learning experiences. Therefore, inquiries on individual and firm characteristics could help to advance the knowledge on to what extent these influence employees' experiencing workplace learning activities. The literature on individual and firm characteristics as predictors of workplace learning is reviewed below.

Employees' age is an important predictor of workplace learning activities experienced by employees. For example, Tikkanen (2002) showed that less experienced, younger employees were exposed to more informal learning activities than their older counterparts. On the contrary, Livingstone (1999) found that older employees were exposed to "as much informal learning as did younger employees". Cerasoli et al. (2018) identified age as a significant contributor to informal learning behaviours. Berg and Chyung (2008) did not find a significant age effect on the degree of informal learning engagement. Daley (1999) reported that inexperienced employees prefer trainers, textbooks, and conferences while experienced employees prefer chances to informally discuss issues with colleagues. These findings suggest that the effect of age on workplace learning activities is not conclusive.

Concerning the effect of sex in experiencing workplace learning activities, Korpi et al. (2013) found that females experienced few learning opportunities compared to males with the same job status. Cerasoli et al. (2018) identified sex as a significant contributor in informal learning behaviours. Further, Manuti et al. (2015) in their review of literature provides evidence of sex inequalities in workplace learning where women facing more barriers in workplace learning. However, Berg and Chyung (2008) did not find a significant gender effect on the degree of informal learning engagement. Concerning marital status as a predictor of learning, Zhao and Mei (2016) identified marital status as a predictor of online learners' learning motivation. Egwualu and Umeora (2007) found marriage, pregnancy, and childbearing as influencing academic performance of older females compared to males, and the difference was

statistically significant. Fontaine (1996) identified marital status as a significant predictor of older adult's participation in self-directed learning.

Concerning the level of education, Berg and Chyung (2008) did not find a significant effect of the level of education on informal learning engagement. However, the studies of Thomas and Qiu (2012) and Roosmaa and Saar (2010) suggest that employees who were more educated and engaged in more prestigious jobs experience more workplace learning activities than others. Further, Cerasoli et al. (2018) found more educated employees seeking out more opportunities for learning, employees in management ranks having a more favourable view for learning programmes than their subordinates; and concluded as these variables having considerable association with informal learning behaviours. As detailed in the section on "Sample", the level of education was not feasible to be included as a variable in our study since the norm of the industry sector is to employ individuals with Bachelor's degrees or equivalent professional qualifications. Further, industry sector and occupation level were not feasible to be included as variables since the study was confined to a single industry sector and respondents were in technical/professional capacities. Therefore, age, gender, marital status, and years of work experience were taken as individual characteristics.

Concerning firm size, the literature identifies firm size as an important variable in workplace learning (Kuchinke, 2003). The argument is that when firm size increases, formal structures, and practices scale up allowing to offer different learning experiences and processes for employees (Bishop, 2020; Marlow et al., 2010). For the present study, the number of full-time employees was taken to represent the firm size. Overall, as reviewed above, since the literature does not provide conclusive evidence for associations between individual and firm characteristics with workplace learning activities, as stated in H2 in the section on *Introduction*, we investigated such associations in our study.

Methodology

Sample

The study was confined to offshore KPO firms located in the Colombo district, which is the commercial hub of the country. A convenience sample of 17 firms volunteered to participate in the survey out of 48 firms identified as the study population of firms that fulfilled the criteria set for the study, i.e., all firms should have at least five years of business existence as offshore KPO service providers. Employees in these firms ranged from approximately 65 to 1800 per firm (sample characteristics are given at the end of this paragraph). Organisation structures of these firms are flat with about two layers of management and the majority of employees can be

identified as technical specialists/professionals. We identified these technical/professional employees, who create value for the firms, as the survey participants. The respondents were performing jobs in the areas such as engineering and design, network consultancy and management, content development, risk assessment and management, animation, equity research, medical research, legal research, and intellectual property research. Firms prefer individuals with Bachelor's degrees or equivalent professional qualifications (such as British Computer Society, Australian Computer Society, Project Management Professional) to perform these job tasks. The criterion adhered to when selecting the sample was possessing at least two years of firm-specific experience at the time of data collection. We believed this amount of minimum firm tenure makes employees aware and experience available workplace learning opportunities and drivers that enhance learning. A contact person was identified from each firm to ease the data collection; one of the authors of this paper together with contact persons distributed the survey questionnaire. The anonymity of the respondents was ensured to reduce evaluation apprehension. We distributed 380 questionnaires and 239 valid responses were received, yielding a response rate of 63%. The respondents came from firms that had an average number of full-time employees of 132 (SD = 81, minimum 97, maximum 1684). Concerning the characteristics of respondents in the final sample, the average age was 28 years (SD = 3.58); 57% were male; 28% identified as married while 71% identified as single inclusive of never married, divorced, separated, and widowed. All had Bachelor's degrees or equivalent professional qualifications; in addition, 17% had postgraduate qualifications. Respondents had an average firm-specific experience of 2.64 years (SD = 2.25, minimum 2 years, maximum 8 years).

Measures

Workplace learning activities. We investigated workplace learning *existed/experienced* by employees in contrast to *important* since all-important workplace learning activities may not be experienced by employees in this sector in Sri Lanka. Hence, we did a preliminary investigation into workplace learning activities that existed in the firms covering both forms of learning - formal and informal (intentional or unintentional) and created a 15-item measure ranging from "never" (1) to "always" (5), where higher scores indicate a higher level of exposure. Therefore, the items reflected the learning activities that prevailed in the firms. These items were first, assessed by a panel of academics and practitioners to ensure the face and content validity. Second, the items were pre-tested with a sample of appropriate employees who were not part of

the final sample to ensure items were worded and complete. Appendix 1 lists the measures used in the study.

Drivers that enhance learning. We investigated drivers that *existed/experienced* by employees. We did a preliminary investigation and created a 21-item measure ranging from "disagree strongly" (1) to "agree strongly" (5), where higher scores indicate a higher level of prevalence. Therefore, the items reflected the situation that prevailed in the firms. As described above, these items were first, assessed by a panel of academics and practitioners to ensure the face and content validity. Second, the items were pre-tested with a sample of appropriate employees who were not part of the final sample to ensure items were worded and complete. Appendix 1 lists the measures used in the study.

Individual and firm characteristics. Sex was coded as "male" (0) and "female" (1). The age was coded as "25 to 40 years" (0) and "41 to 55 years" (1). Marital status was coded as "single" (0, to include categories of never married, separated, divorced, or widowed) and "married" (1). Age, firm tenure, and the number of employees in the firm were collected on a ratio scale.

Method of data collection

The data collection instrument was the survey questionnaire in the English language, which is considered as a national language of the country. It was in three parts. Questions on workplace learning activities were given in part one; questions on drivers that enhance learning were given in part two, and questions relating to individual and firm characteristics were given in part three. We adhered to the sample selection criteria stipulated in the section on *Sample*, and each individual responded to all three sections in the survey. Upon data collection, the measures were subjected to appropriate internal consistency reliability, factor structure, convergent validity, discriminant validity and construct reliability, as detailed in the section on *Methods of data analysis*.

Methods of data analysis

Data were tested for common method variance using Harman's single-factor test; neither single factor emerged from this analysis nor was there a general factor that could account for the majority of variance fulfilling the recommended guidelines (refer to Hair et al., 2006). According to Hair et al. (2006, p.173-177) and Brace et al. (2006, p.328-329), the technique of rotation should be devised to simplify the solution to the factor analysis. For the study, one of the Orthogonal rotation methods, namely, Varimax, was used since it is identified as giving the

rotated factors that are easiest to interpret. Since the intention of this paper is to reach a wide audience with both quantitative and qualitative readers, Principal component factor analysis with Varimax rotation was performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Data were tested for appropriate (a) internal consistency reliability, (b) factor structure (c) convergent validity, (d) discriminant validity, and (e) construct reliability (CR) to identify any issues with multicollinearity and response bias. Convergent validity was measured by average variance extracted (AVE) and discriminant validity was measured by the square root of AVE. The criteria adhered to are: eigenvalues of all components should not be less than 1.0; the loadings should be 0.50 or greater to be considered practically significant; Cronbach's alpha values of each factor extracted and overall measure should be greater than 0.7; AVE values should be above 0.5; the square root of AVE for a given construct should be greater than the correlation between that construct and all other constructs (refer to Hair et al., 2006). Multiple regression analysis was used to identify the association between drivers of workplace learning and the type of learning activities experienced by employees (H1) and whether age, gender, marital status and the years of work experience of employees and the number of employees in the firm are associated with workplace learning activities experienced by employees (H2). When running the regression analyses, all variables relating to the individual and firm characteristics were entered into the model as the first step. Independent variables (drivers) were entered in the second step (for a detailed description, see Hair et al., 2006). Beta coefficient (β) and the adjusted coefficient of determination (adjusted R^2) were used to interpret the results of regression analysis.

Results

The 15-item measure on workplace learning was subjected to factor analysis. The analysis yielded three factors as shown in Table 1. These factors were named as formal learning activities, learning from peers and superiors, and self-initiated learning activities. The factors explained 67% (67.44) of the variance. The 21-item measure on drivers that enhance learning yielded three factors as shown in Table 2. These factors were named as organisation-related, individual-related, and team-related. The factors explained 65% (65.04) of the variance. Table 3 shows descriptive statistics and correlations between the variables.

Tables 1, 2, and 3 about here

Regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses. The results are summarised in Table 4. With regard to formal learning activities, organisation-related ($\beta = .312, p < 0.001$), individual-related ($\beta = .264, p < 0.001$) and team-related ($\beta = .210, p < 0.001$) drivers had significant positive effects; organisation-related drivers had the highest effect. With regard to learning from peers and superiors, organisation-related ($\beta = .229, p < 0.001$), individual-related ($\beta = .248, p < 0.001$) and team-related ($\beta = .233, p < 0.001$) drivers had significant positive effects; individual-related drivers had the highest effect. With regard to self-initiated learning activities, organisation-related ($\beta = .212, p < 0.001$), individual-related ($\beta = .388, p < 0.001$) and team-related ($\beta = .200, p < 0.001$) drivers had significant positive effects; individual-related drivers had the highest effect. Since all three types of drivers significantly positively predicted all three workplace learning activities, H1 is supported. The adjusted R^2 of .410 reveals that the final model explained 41% of the variance in the formal learning activities ($p < 0.001$); the adjusted R^2 of .379 reveals that the final model explained 38% of the variance in learning from peers and superiors ($p < 0.001$); the adjusted R^2 of .442 reveals that the final model explained 44% of the variance in self-initiated learning activities ($p < 0.001$). Further, Table 4 (step 1 and 2) show that firm-specific experience and the number of employees in the firm significantly predicted all three types of learning activities. Further, age had a significant negative effect on learning from peers and superiors and self-initiated learning activities, implying that younger employees experienced these activities more than their older counterparts. Overall, H2 is partially supported.

Table 4 about here

Discussion of findings and implications

The present study investigated workplace learning activities experienced by employees working in IT-enabled work environments for the successful completion of work-related job tasks at hand and drivers that enhanced workplace learning. As presented above, we found that employees experienced a variety of workplace learning activities, which were grouped into three- formal learning activities, learning from peers and superiors, and self-initiated learning activities. Of these, the most experienced type was formal learning activities (% of the variance explained = 27.88). This contradicts the literature reviewed earlier. Still, building on the literature reviewed earlier, it is possible to interpret this finding as relating to employees' awareness of workplace learning activities. The second most experienced type was learning from peers and superiors (%

of the variance explained = 25.72) such as knowledge sharing sessions, mentoring relationships, interacting with others via blogs, and guidance from the immediate superior. Employees self-initiate learning activities and learn through their information-seeking processes such as specific searches of the Internet and Intranet to fulfil requirements of job tasks at hand. Previous studies such as Milligan et al. (2014) also found that the nature of work makes employees to self-initiate learning activities. With compared to the first two types of learning activities, learning from the third type- self-initiated learning activities- is low (% of the variance explained = 13.83). However, it is possible to expect that employees will self-initiate more learning activities and they will be exposed to more open and networked content in their task performance over the years to come.

Over the past two decades, the workplace has emerged as an important location where learning occurs (see Billett, 2015; Clow, 2013; Milligan et al., 2014). We used the term *drivers that enhance learning* with a much broader meaning to include processes and systems that are created by organisations as well as drivers that are not related to the organisation (such as the enthusiasm of an employee to learn). The factor analysis yielded three types of drivers- organisation-related, individual-related, and team-related. Of the three, organisation-related and individual-related drivers accounted for a relatively larger share compared to team-related. Some of the organisation-related drivers include the existence of regular performance evaluations, processes to establish gaps between expected and actual performance, the maintenance of skill inventories, the availability of suitable trainers, the development of appropriate infrastructure (such as Internet and Intranet), access for employees to obtain information without difficulty, and the appropriate design of work (Table 2). Some of the individual-related drivers include employees' job context, enthusiasm, awareness of developments related to the job role, and employees' energy towards learning. In other words, the findings suggest that the individual-related drivers are more dependent on what employees' experience and the job itself provides reasons for them to learn through various means. Previous studies such as Crouse et al. (2011) also revealed that employees find reasons to initiate learning through job-related issues. Some of the team-related drivers include team communication, team conflict resolution, support for each other's learning among team members, and agreement with organisation's mission and objectives. The results revealed that organization-related, individual-related, and team-related drivers significantly positively predict the three types of learning activities. Still, the effect of organisation-related drivers is the strongest for formal learning activities, and the effect of individual-related drivers is the strongest for both self-initiated activities and learning from peers and superiors. Concerning the effect of individual and firm characteristics on learning activities

experienced by employees, age was significant in predicting learning from peers and superiors and learning from self-initiated activities, where young employees experiencing these more often. Firm-specific tenure and the number of employees in the firm were significant in predicting all the types of learning activities experienced by employees. The findings of the study have implications for both theory and practice, which are discussed below.

Implications of the findings for the existing literature. The study bridges the gap in the literature on six spheres. First, the present study investigated workplace learning in one of the new forms of business sectors, about which limited empirical studies are available. The outcomes of these new forms of work structures on employees and work systems are still under discussion. To support the process-based and team-based work organization, these firms use a flatter organisational structure, and the workforce is largely comprised of educated technical/professional personnel performing their job tasks in an IT-enabled work environment. Although it is argued that these forms of work organisations have the potential to provide a more favourable learning environment, the number of empirical studies conducted in these are limited (such as Milligan et al., 2014).

Second, the findings suggest that employees largely engage in organisation sponsored formal learning activities followed by learning from peers and superiors. Concerning formal learning activities, opportunities provided through in-house experts, demonstrations, and guest speakers were found to be frequent. One reason for this finding may be that our sample consisted of technical/professional employees, and much of the learning is for knowledge and skill acquisition through sponsored formal means. The use of e-learning had become the norm; e-learning is not an option as suggested by Crouse et al. (2011) and Berg and Chyung (2008). Previous studies such as Morris et al. (2005) suggested some generational effects of IT use for learning activities. However, in the present day, IT skills have become a must for individuals' survival for employment. Concerning learning from peers and superiors, knowledge sharing sessions, mentoring relationships, guidance from immediate superior, and interacting with others via blogs were found to be frequent. Learning from blogs suggests that learning no longer emerges from face-to-face or known experts/colleagues. Discussions with colleagues may be mediated by IT and physical proximity may not be very much existing. Our findings contradict with Berg and Chyung (2008), who identified learning activities to be mostly connected to talking with colleagues and physical proximity to colleagues. Further, Berg and Chyung (2008) separated the type of learning activities and computer technology when discussing learning from colleagues, and stated: "one should differentiate that 'computer technology' is a tool for participating in informal learning activities, whereas 'talking with colleagues' is an informal

learning activity” (239). However, in the present environment, learning activities cannot be separated from information and communication technologies. This applies to workplace learning activities irrespective of whether the organisation operates in the developed world or developing world. Concerning learning from self-initiated activities, the findings of our study imply that employees consume resources created by others by researching solutions, reading, and searching the Internet and Intranet. Therefore, self-initiated learning activities that emerged in the study, on one hand, can be identified as more passive approaches since employees use knowledge sources created by others. On the other hand, these learning activities can be identified as more active since employees learn through self-directed researching/searching. The findings also suggest that the consumption of knowledge alone is insufficient; employees did not solely rely on researching solutions, reading, and searching. Along with these, they used learning activities connected to peers and superiors, which could assist them in the sense-making process of consumed knowledge.

Third, the findings suggest an interplay between three types of drivers that enhance learning emerged in the study in predicting each type of learning activity. Organisation-related drivers imply that organisations have to be innovative in creating systems to monitor employee performance, manage employees’ skill inventories, and get maximum out of organisation-based trainers and mentors in support of workplace learning. Further, team-related drivers imply that the way decision making happens in teams, routine and non-routine problem-solving, feedback, guidance, and support from peers and superiors are important in supporting learning. Previous studies such as Billett (2015) and Lans et al. (2016) also highlighted the importance of these types of drivers for workplace learning. Our findings suggest that team reflections at regular intervals help employees to perform work effectively and adjust their behaviour to suit the work situation, which could ultimately lead to process improvements within teams. We also found that a team’s awareness of organisations direction and strategies help in learning. Hence, organizations should identify more effective means and create rich learning experiences to support team interactions. Furthermore, individual-related drivers such as individual employees’ enthusiasm make them initiate learning activities to suit their job roles. Previous studies such as Rausch (2013) also stated the importance of job task characteristics in influencing learning initiatives; Kolb (1984) stated the importance of immediate personnel job experiences when learning from reflection. Individual learning goal orientation could also be an important factor behind self-initiated learning activities. In this regard, previous studies such as Kyndt et al. (2014) and Nitsche et al. (2011) state that individuals with learning goal orientation work

towards enhancing their capabilities and make choices on learning activities appropriate for goal achievement.

Fourth, concerning the explanatory potential of individual and firm characteristics as predictors of learning activities, employees' firm tenure and the number of employees in the firm were identified as significant in predicting learning activities. When firm-specific experience increases, employees experience more learning from peers and superiors and self-initiate more learning activities. This supports the findings of Daley (1999), who reported inexperienced employees' preference for more formal learning activities. Age is a significant predictor of learning from peers and superiors and self-initiated learning activities, where younger employees experienced these activities more than their older counterparts. Previous studies such as Tikkanen (2002) also provided evidence for the same. Concerning the number of employees in the firm, the results implied that employees attached to the firms with a large workforce experience more learning from peers and superiors and self-initiate more learning activities. Our findings support Marlow et al. (2010), who showed that when firm size increases, employees are exposed to a variety of learning experiences and processes.

Fifth, since the study is conducted on employees in IT-enabled work environments, the findings have the potential to be used in the current day's new normal context. Since the Covid-19 pandemic, all forms of organisations irrespective of the location (rural/urban within a country or developed/developing countries) have to rely on IT-enabled work environments making organisations more uniform than otherwise. The present work environment made many connections between employees and between employees and the organisation virtual (see Arora and Suri, 2020). However, this situation is not an exception for workplace learning (Bierema, 2020; Li et al., 2020; Yawson, 2020). Although our study is not on employees' learning during the pandemic, we presented findings of a study that investigated learning activities and drivers enhancing learning as experienced by employees in a IT-enabled work context. Therefore, the findings of our study provide valuable insight on how workplace learning occurs and drivers that support workplace learning in IT-enabled work environments.

Sixth, the boundary of workplace learning is potentially constrained by the perception of the "workplace" (Clow, 2013; Matthews, 1999). In the present day, the workplace should not be confined to the physical "workplace" location, within which employees perform their job roles. An employee can physically locate outside the workplace, like at home, and identify him/her as an integral part of the "workplace" (Matthews, 1999). Since the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic, the world is witnessing more than half of the workforce is working remotely relying on IT-enabled work environments. The literature (such as Arora and Suri, 2020; Dirani et al.,

2020; Li et al., 2020) emphasizes that organisations worldwide have to re-think the process of providing workplace learning opportunities for employees irrespective of the scale and the nature of the business. In this regard, we provided employees' experiences of workplace learning in IT-enabled work environments. Therefore, we believe that the findings of our study have more relevance and provide useful information to bridge the knowledge gap in the literature.

Seventh, the study was conducted in Sri Lanka, an Asian developing country. When it comes to KPO operations, the Western developed countries outsource these activities to developing countries like Sri Lanka. Hence, this type of study in developing countries is the major source for enhancing the current body of literature. Therefore, we believe our study contributed to the knowledge on workplace learning, which is primarily based on Western examples. Further, the literature reviewed did not provide conclusive evidence for the effect of individual and firm characteristics of workplace learning. Our study provided evidence that employees' firm tenure, age, and the number of employees in the firm were significantly associated with learning activities experienced by employees. This also highlights the need of understanding more about individual and firm characteristics, and their associations with workplace learning, which warrants more future research.

Implications of the findings for practice. The findings have implications for employees, organisations as well as other stakeholders such as policymakers. First, the findings implied the importance of developing personal skills such as reflection, maintaining learning networks through teamwork, use of blogs, and the ability to self-regulate own learning. This also implies the importance of developing essential and practical learning behaviours in the work setting. In short, employees have to develop a certain set of skills that are not thought by the formal education system of a country. This is very true for the work environment created in the new normal. Although it is possible to see worldwide changes in how work has to be performed under the new normal, employees across countries may not be equally exposed to the type of learning activities required and tools to be used to remain deployable for the survival in the respective labour market in the new normal. In this regard, Raemdonck et al. (2014, p. 189) state “workers have to engage in targeted learning that enables them to learn what they need to know, when they need to know it”.

Second, organization-related drivers influence all three types of workplace learning activities- sponsored by organisations, chosen by peers and superiors for collective advancement as well as self-initiated by individuals. The findings showed that work provides an inducement for teams to use and individuals to self-initiate learning activities. It is clear that job tasks

assigned and those need to be completed through social interactions with peers in teams provide learning opportunities. Belonging to a particular community-of-practice such as a work unit or team makes employees choose *the same* learning activities to fulfil similar job tasks. Hence, when job tasks become similar, employees may find *the same* learning activities are required since they need *the same* capabilities to perform those; organisations may also find that *the same* learning opportunities are effective and will sponsor *the same*. Since the team-related features are important in predicting workplace learning activities, organisations should pay more attention to the design of teamwork and the selection/assignment of team members.

Third, in connection to the above, organizations should maintain proper systems for managing people such as performance evaluation and human resource development. The findings also showed the importance of communicating organisation's mission and strategic objectives across employees. Further, organisations have a role to play in maintaining drivers that enhance learning. Furthermore, a close inspection of learning activities self-initiated by employees such as reading a book/journal and internet searches suggests that the relative cost of these is low. Fourth, the findings imply the responsibility of organisations for developing employees' skills such as understanding self, the personal meaning of learning, and the sense of ownership and self-control. These will be essential to thrive in the new normal. At the same time, organisations should develop the skills of senior managers as potential mentors, coaches, and facilitators, and the skills of team leaders to provide proper leadership for team-based learning activities.

Fifth, Van Rijn et al. (2013) stated "informal workplace learning is initiated by the employees themselves and takes place during work and at the workplace" (p. 611), which implies at the physical workplace. However, in the present day, the demarcation between work location- physical and virtual- is difficult. The workplace landscape has changed substantially due to the Covid-19 pandemic. One of the strengths of the present study is our respondents were in IT-enabled work environments. We believe that our findings could provide valuable insight in transforming learning into a more virtual environment with the use of information and communication technologies. Sixth, when workplace learning is seen as spanning from the formal education system of a country, it has the responsibility to ensure that its products survive and succeed across working life. This is especially important under the new normal. In this regard, Clarke (2005) found that vocational learners lacked skills needed to be self-directed, self-control, and independent and also lacked inclination for self-initiated learning. Therefore, adult education systems need to bridge any gaps in computer literacy, information literacy and need to ensure their citizens are self-directed and more independent.

Conclusion

The findings revealed that employees experienced a variety of workplace learning activities and drivers that enhance workplace learning; drivers significantly predict the type of learning activities experienced by employees. Organisations have a greater share in the creation and maintenance of organization and team-related drivers and supporting/encouraging individual-related drivers through a variety of interventions in the workplace. When organisation, team, and individual-related drivers operate within the workplace, employees may get the maximum use from sponsored formal learning opportunities, participate in communities of practice, seek out appropriate learning from peers and superiors as well as self-initiate learning activities. Employees' exposure to a variety of learning activities may bring about expected learning outcomes at the workplace. Employees' firm tenure, age, and the number of employees in the firm were also significant in the prediction of learning activities experienced by employees. Findings have both implications for theory and practice, which were discussed in the above sections.

Limitations and future research

As in all research studies, the present study also has some limitations, which could open many future research possibilities. First, we conceptualized workplace learning activities and drivers in terms of "experienced" in contrast to "important". We believe that respondents may indicate importance even to those they have not experienced in the workplace. However, we have not investigated the effectiveness of these experienced learning activities, which is a limitation of the study. Future research could investigate not only learning activities but also the effectiveness of the activities in job performance. When it comes to the effectiveness of learning activities, not only the acquisition and use are important but the creation of knowledge is also important. Future research could incorporate this aspect.

Second, the study investigated learning activities in connection to fulfilling jobs at hand or immediate job performance. Still, the respondents were not instructed to distinguish informal intended and informal unintended learning activities assuming they may find difficulties in doing so. Third, we operationalised the term drivers broadly and factor analysis yielded three factors. Future research could perform in-depth investigations on each of these. Further, the present work environment not only demands more stringent tools to facilitate learning but also to monitor and evaluate employees' learning. In this regard, the present business environment adds more constraints to organisations. Therefore, future research could investigate the

mechanisms organisations use or planning to use in the delivery and evaluation of workplace learning in the new normal.

Fourth, our findings suggest that age has more explanatory potential on learning from peers and superiors and learning from self-initiated activities. Future research could investigate the use and effectiveness of workplace learning activities between older and younger employees, which will also shed light on the future employability of employees belonging to different age categories in the new normal. In connection to the above, future research could investigate the extent of informal intended learning occur in virtual spaces, and behaviours of employees belonging to different age categories in managing to learn such as monitoring and optimizing in virtual contexts. Last but not least, more research is needed to understand the explanatory potential of firm characteristics on workplace learning activities.

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Tables

Table 1. Workplace learning activities

	F1: Formal learning activities	F2: Learning from peers and superiors	F3: Self-initiated learning activities
I learn from managerial games/outbound training	.80		
I learn from guest speakers who attend events of my organization	.79		
I learn from certification courses offered	.77		
I learn from development activities, not necessarily for job role and designation (such as time management, health, and safety)	.75		
I learn from demonstrations	.67		
I learn from mandatory training for job role and designation	.66		
I learn from knowledge sharing at work		.86	
I learn by working with others		.74	
I learn from supervision and guidance provided		.74	
I learn from career consultation received from my mentor		.68	
I learn by interacting with other people via email/blogs		.66	
I learn from feedback received from others		.65	
I learn by researching solutions to problems at hand			.79
I learn from intranet resources and internet search			.76
I learn by reading books/journals/industry magazines and job-related documents			.72
Eigenvalue	4.18	3.86	2.07
% of variance (rotation sums of squared loadings)	27.89	25.72	13.83
Cronbach's alpha	.901	.874	.727
AVE	.55	.53	.57
Construct reliability	.88	.87	.80

Table 2. Drivers enhancing learning

	F1: Organization -related	F2: Individual -related	F3: Team- related
Exposure to sequenced challenging work design helps me learn	.81		
My organization enables employees to access needed information at any time (such as via Intranet)	.79		
My organization encourages employees to ask questions regardless of rank	.78		
There are capable trainers in my organization	.77		
My organization administers sufficient training programmes to suit job role and designation	.76		
My organization maintains an up-to-date inventory of employee skills	.75		
My organization has a system to measure gaps between current and expected performance	.71		
My organization administers appropriate training programmes to suit job role and designation	.65		
My organization administers regular performance evaluation	.61		
My awareness of critical issues of my work makes me look for learning opportunities		.86	
My enthusiasm to be current and knowledgeable about my field of work make me look for learning opportunities		.85	
I have a high level of energy to devote to learning		.81	
Breadth of my job role encourages me to learn new things		.68	
Depth of my job role encourages me to learn new things		.66	
Teams follow the vision, mission, and goals of the organization			.84
Teams use two-way communication regularly			.82
Teams use conflict resolution techniques during team discussions			.77
Sharing of success/achievement among team members helps to learn			.75
Teams treat members as equals, regardless of rank or other differences			.72
Peer to peer support helps team learning			.71
Team meetings help to generate new ideas			.70
Eigenvalue	3.56	3.54	3.30
% of variance (rotation sums of squared loadings)	22.27	22.14	20.63
Cronbach's alpha	.843	.899	.861
AVE	.51	.60	.55
Construct reliability	.86	.88	.86

Table 3. Correlation

	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1 Age	27.85	3.58	-										
2 Sex [◇]	-	-	.128	-									
3 Marital status [◇]	-	-	.518**	.014	-								
4 Experience (firm)	2.64	2.25	.562**	.121	.103	-							
5 Number of employees [±]	-	-	.110	.045	.024	.128	-						
6 Organization-related	4.13	1.34	.169*	.147*	.104	.123	.251**	.71					
7 Individual-related	4.78	1.20	-.132*	.121	.049	.209**	.250**	.218**	.77				
8 Team-related	5.10	1.12	-.098	.124	.040	.225**	.269**	.231**	.340**	.74			
9 Formal learning activities	5.99	.71	.112	.059	.090	.140*	.257**	.398**	.387**	.276**	.74		
10 Learning from peers and superiors	5.83	.845	-.160*	.159*	.008	.261**	.300**	.275**	.342**	.310**	.355**	.73	
11 Self-initiated learning activities	5.76	.87	-.203**	.170*	.073	.276**	.247**	.269**	.486**	.256**	.411**	.409**	.75

Note: [◇] in nominal scale; [±] in log ln; * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$; diagonal entries, square root of AVE where appropriate; off-diagonal entries, correlation between constructs.

Table 4. Regression results

Step	Variable	Formal learning activities					Learning from peers and superiors					Self-initiated learning activities				
		<i>beta</i>	R ² (Adj)	Change statistics			<i>beta</i>	R ² (Adj)	Change statistics			<i>beta</i>	R ² (Adj)	Change statistics		
				R ² Change	F Change	Sig. of F Change			R ² Change	F Change	Sig. of F Change			R ² Change	F Change	Sig. of F Change
1	Age	.064	.058	.084	3.10	P<.05	-.109*	.061	.068	4.32	P<.05	-.116*	.072	.078	5.79	P<.05
	Sex	.011					.028					.024				
	Marital status	.017					.024					.029				
	Experience (firm)	.102*					.108*					.123*				
	Number of employees	.109*					.116*					.119*				
2	Age	.069	.410	.341	98.53	p < 0.001	-.114*	.379	.315	77.46	p < 0.001	-.122*	.442	.375	98.57	p < 0.001
	Sex	.037					.036					.049				
	Marital status	.026					.020					.025				
	Experience (firm)	.113*					.114*					.119*				
	Number of employees	.112*					.118*					.119*				
	Organization-related	.312***					.229***					.212***				
	Individual-related	.264***					.248***					.388***				
	Team-related	.210***					.233***					.200***				

Note: * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$

Appendix 1. Item measures

Workplace learning activities (1 = “never” to 5 = “always”)

I learn from managerial games/outbound training
I learn from guest speakers who attend events of my organization
I learn from certification courses offered
I learn from development activities, not necessarily for job role and designation (such as time management, health, and safety)
I learn from demonstrations
I learn from mandatory training for job role and designation
I learn from knowledge sharing at work
I learn by working with others
I learn from supervision and guidance provided
I learn from career consultation received from my mentor
I learn by interacting with other people via email/blogs
I learn from feedback received from others
I learn by researching solutions to problems at hand
I learn from intranet resources and internet search
I learn by reading books/journals/industry magazines and job-related documents

Drivers enhancing learning (1 = "disagree strongly" to 5 = "agree strongly")

Exposure to sequenced challenging work design helps me learn
My organization enables employees to access needed information at any time (such as via Intranet)
My organization encourages employees to ask questions regardless of rank
There are capable trainers in my organization
My organization administers sufficient training programmes to suit job role and designation
My organization maintains an up-to-date inventory of employee skills
My organization has a system to measure gaps between current and expected performance
My organization administers appropriate training programmes to suit job role and designation
My organization administers regular performance evaluation
My awareness of critical issues of my work makes me look for learning opportunities
My enthusiasm to be current and knowledgeable about my field of work make me look for learning opportunities
I have a high level of energy to devote to learning
Breadth of my job role encourages me to learn new things
Depth of my job role encourages me to learn new things
Teams follow the vision, mission, and goals of the organization
Teams use two-way communication regularly
Teams use conflict resolution techniques during team discussions
Sharing of success/achievement among team members helps to learn
Teams treat members as equals, regardless of rank or other differences
Peer to peer support helps team learning
Team meetings help to generate new ideas